

A STUDY OF MALONYLGUANIDINE AND ITS REACTIVE METHYLENE GROUP. PART I. CONDENSATION OF MALONYLGUANIDINE WITH AROMATIC ALDEHYDES UNDER STRONG ACIDIC CONDITIONS

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Malonylguanidine condenses with aryl aldehydes in the presence of acetic acid-sulphuric acid mixture (ca. 4 : 1) to give arylidene-malonylguanidine sulphates $\text{ArCH} : [(\text{C}_4\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}_2)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$. In the presence of hydrogen chloride in saturation with absolute alcohol or acetic acid, the products are either an arylidene-malonylguanidine chloride $\text{ArCH} : [(\text{C}_4\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{HCl}]$ or compounds of the bis-type $\text{ArCH} : [(\text{C}_4\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{HCl}]_2$, depending upon the nature of the aldehydes.

Barbituric acid is known to give with aromatic aldehydes 5-arylidene-barbituric acids,

even by warming the ureide and the aldehyde in aqueous or alcoholic solutions and without the use of any condensing agent (Conrad and Reinback, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 1339; Weinschenk, *ibid.*, p. 1685). With thiobarbituric acid (Dox and Plaisance, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 2164) the 5-arylidene-2-thiobarbituric acids are smoothly obtained from aldehydes, but 12% hydrochloric acid is needed to effect condensation. Certain NN'-disubstituted barbituric acids and thiobarbituric acids (Whitley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **91**, 1342; Akabori, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1931, **52**, 601; *Ber.*, 1933, **66B**, 139; Whitley and Mountain, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **25**, 121) can also be condensed more or less with the same ease as the parent ureides. It is remarkable that barbituric acid and salicylaldehyde upon direct condensation (Conrad and Reinback, *loc. cit.*, p. 1340) yield 5'-salicyl-bis-barbituric acid:

Condensation products from benzaldehyde and certain phenolic aldehydes in the presence of acetic acid are reported also to be of the *bis*-type (Pavoline, *Riv. Ital. essenza. Profumi*, 1933, 18, 171). In the above cases the condensation products are generally coloured, though in the case of less substituted aldehydes colorless forms are also met with. The compounds from the barbitric acids are decomposed with aqueous caustic soda or ammonium hydroxide with the separation of the aldehyde in a way, perhaps, typical of the reversal of an aldol reaction (cf. equation 1).

In comparison of barbituric acid, thiobarbituric acid and malonylguanidine as a quantitative precipitant for furfural in very dilute solutions, Dox and Plaisance (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 2156) report incidentally the formation of furfurylidene-malonylguanidine $C_4H_5OCH : C_4H_3N_3O_2$ in the presence of 12% hydrochloric acid. Apart from the above meagre reference little is known so far about the reactivity of malonylguanidine. In the present investigation the results obtained by condensing malonylguanidine with various aldehydes in alcohol and acetic acid under strong acidic conditions are recorded.

When malonylguanidine is reacted with benzaldehyde in the presence of glacial acetic acid-sulphuric acid mixture (4: 1), a well defined crystalline product is obtained, which has the composition

the sulphuric acid remaining chemically bound to the condensation product. The acetic acid-sulphuric acid mixture serves also as a solvent for malonylguanidine which is difficult to dissolve in any other organic solvent except formic acid. Other aldehydes e. g., 4-chlorobenzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 4-nitrobenzaldehyde, β -resorcylic aldehyde, pyrogallol aldehyde and vanillin can be condensed with more or less equal ease giving products which are always coloured and contain combined acid. The latter is apparently released in cold water though by this treatment the solids invariably retain their original colour. On prolonged contact with water or upon heating, further decomposition occurs regenerating the malonylguanidine and the aldehyde. Decomposition is quicker with aqueous alkalis but is attended with the appearance of transient violet colorations in the case of phenolic compounds. All the products have the composition of an arylidene-malonylguanidine sulphate, formed thus,

Reaction can occur also when hydrogen chloride gas, dissolved in absolute alcohol or glacial acetic acid, is used as the condensing agent. But the nature of the product seems to depend upon the aldehyde used. Vanillin, β -resorcylic aldehyde, pyrogallol aldehyde and furfural give an arylidene-malonylguanidine chloride

in which curiously enough only one molecule of hydrochloric acid remains attached to the resulting product. On the other hand, benzaldehyde and 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde

give compounds having the composition of a bis-malonylguanidine derivative

The arylidene-malonylguanidine chlorides behave more or less like their sulphate analogues but the bis-type of compounds are very soluble in cold water, though they also are hydrolytically decomposed with equal ease. The latter salts are, however, faintly coloured compared to the arylidene sulphates or chlorides, some of which are highly coloured.

The analogous mode of the hydrolytic decomposition of the products from malonylguanidine and from barbitruic acid is suggestive of the reactive methylene group in malonylguanidine being involved in the reaction. The unsaturated character of the arylidene-malonylguanidine sulphates and chlorides is in accord with this view point.

The above reactions can be explained if we consider that malonylguanidine is a "zwitterion" such as (II).

This internal salt-like arrangement is justified by the properties of malonylguanidine itself. As in the form (II) there is no incipiently ionised hydrogen atom, malonylguanidine is unable to condense with aldehydes directly like barbituric acid. However, in the presence of strong mineral acid, the zwitterion character is lost and a salt with the acid will be formed thus,

(X = Cl⁻ or HSO₄⁻)

the glacial acetic acid or the alcohol serving the purpose of a solvent for the salt (III). In this way the reactive methylene group is made available for condensation, as it is in barbituric acid, with the difference that here a cation, e. g., from (III) is the reactive entity, instead of a neutral molecule. On this basis, the products holding only one equivalent of sulphuric acid (vide equation 3) should be deemed as acid salts. In an analogous way the bis-type of the compounds may also be formulated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Malonylguanidine.—It was best prepared and purified according to the method of Dass and Dutt (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1939, 9, 93) from malonic ester and guanidine carbonate. In addition malonylguanidine was found to dissolve in warm (80°) formic acid from which it could be recrystallised; it failed to dissolve in several other non-polar solvents tried.

Malonylguanidine did not condense with benzaldehyde in the presence of absolute alcohol. The addition of sodium ethoxide evolved ammonia on continued heating indicating the occurrence of secondary decompositions. The use of glacial acetic acid or acetic anhydride was equally ineffective. Also, in the bare solvents used the malonylguanidine had remained practically insoluble. Finally, the following acidic mixtures were found to give products of uniform composition and had the added advantage of serving as a solvent for malonylguanidine:

- (i) Conc. sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) diluted to 100 c.c. with glacial acetic acid.
- (ii) Absolute alcohol saturated with hydrogen chloride gas.
- (iii) Glacial acetic acid saturated with hydrogen chloride gas.

Condensation of Malonylguanidine with Benzaldehyde in the presence of Glacial Acetic Acid-Sulphuric Acid Mixture.—The acid mixture (12.7 c.c.) was added quickly to malonylguanidine (1.27 g., 0.01 M) with vigorous stirring and slight warming on the water-bath, when all the guanidine practically went in solution. If the required amount of the solvent was not used at once, a part of the malonylguanidine tended to form a gelatinous product which failed to be redissolved in excess of the solvent. The clear liquid was decanted off from a few undissolved particles into a boiling tube containing a solution of benzaldehyde (1.6 g., 0.015 M) in glacial acetic acid (5 c.c.) and the mixture was heated on a water-bath at 80°-90° with occasional stirring. After 10 minutes, yellow feathery crystals began to appear, which increased considerably afterwards. Upon cooling, the whole crop of crystals was filtered, washed repeatedly with glacial acetic acid till the washings ceased to give any precipitate with aq. barium chloride. They were then further washed with carbon tetrachloride to remove acetic acid and dried at 90°. The product was pure enough but could be recrystallised from formic acid.

The compound was light yellow, showing leaflets under the microscope, m.p. 236-38° (decomp.). It decolorised quickly 1% potassium permanganate and bromine water in the cold. On boiling with water it decomposed to give a strong smell of

benzaldehyde and the aqueous filtrate gave a precipitate with barium chloride. The latter test could also be obtained from a suspension of the compound in cold water. Dissolution occurred also in aqueous alkali and concentrated sulphuric acid; it was followed by decomposition in the first case and colour change to golden yellow in the last case. {Found: N, 12.3; H₂SO₄ (after aq. decomp.), 30.21. [C₆H₅CH : C₄H₅N₃O₂].H₂SO₄ requires N, 13.41; H₂SO₄, 31.4 per cent). Yield 1.68 g. (56%).

Preparation of various Arylidene-malonylguanidine Sulphates.—Condensations were run, as in the previous experiment, with various aldehydes (0.015 to 0.02 M). Of all the solvents tried formic acid had excellent solvent properties for the resulting products, which themselves had crystallised out from the reaction mixture more or less in the pure form. They were decomposed by hot water and aqueous alkalis, with the evolution of strong characteristic smell of the aldehyde, e. g., in the compounds with 4-chloro-, 4-methoxy-, 2-hydroxy-, 3-methoxy-, and 4-hydroxybenzaldehydes. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolved them giving yellow-orange solutions. With phenolic compounds, however, aqueous alkali gave also transient violet colorations and concentrated sulphuric acid produced charring. The compounds from 3-hydroxy-, 4-methoxy-, 3-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehydes were also slightly soluble in ether, chloroform and hot acetic acid. In every case the products decolorised 1% potassium permanganate. The test for unsaturation with bromine water, as applied to the non-phenolic compounds, was also given. Table I summarises the chief results obtained, those from benzaldehyde being also incorporated for the sake of completeness.

Condensation of Malonylguanidine with Benzaldehyde and 3-Hydroxybenzaldehyde in the presence of Absolute Alcohol saturated with Hydrogen Chloride.—The malonylguanidine (0.635 g., 0.005 M) was gradually dissolved in alcoholic hydrogen chloride (35 c.c.) and after filtration from a few undissolved particles, reacted with a solution of benzaldehyde (0.53 g., 0.005 M) in acetic acid (3 c.c.) in a boiling tube. The mixture was stirred and warmed at 40°-50° and kept overnight. The crystals that had separated were washed first with acetic acid and then repeatedly with chloroform till the washings ceased to give a precipitate with aqueous silver nitrate. They were then dried at 90°.

The compound had a faint yellow colour. It charred at 244° and decomposed with frothing at 256°. It was very soluble in cold water which deposited white granular mass on keeping. By this treatment also the aqueous liquid smelt freely of benzaldehyde. The aqueous filtrate gave a precipitate with aqueous silver nitrate, insoluble in nitric acid. Decomposition was quicker with aqueous alkalis. It dissolved in formic acid and concentrated sulphuric acid with evolution of hydrogen chloride in the latter case. {Found: N, 19.82; HCl (after alkaline decomposition and weighed as AgCl), 17.7. C₆H₅CH : [C₄H₅N₃O₂.HCl]₂ requires N, 20.24; HCl, 17.58 per cent}. Yield 0.7 g. (61.3%).

In a similar experiment with 3-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.91 g., 0.075 M) crystals appeared after 1½ hours at room temperature and the reaction was completed by keeping overnight. The product has its properties like the compound with benzaldehyde, m.p. 242-46° (decomp.). {Found: N, 19.5; HCl, 17.1. HO.C₆H₄CH : [(C₄H₅N₃O₂.HCl)]₂ requires N, 19.03; HCl, 16.93 per cent}. Yield 0.9 g. (67.1%).

TABLE I

Ar-CHO & wt.	Formation of the compound.	Yield.		Colour, shape & decomp. point.	Arylidene-malonylguanidine sulphate. (Ar ^x CH : C ₄ H ₃ N ₃ O ₂ · H ₂ SO ₄)			
					Nitrogen		H ₂ SO ₄	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
C ₆ H ₅ .CHO (1-Benzaldehyde 1.6 g., 0.015 M)	After 10 mins. heating	1.68 g.	56.0%	Yellow leaflets; decomp. 236-38°	12.30	13.47	30.21	31.40
(Cl).C ₆ H ₄ .CHO 4 1 (1.4 g., 0.01 M)	After 5 mins. heating.	2.20	63.1	Yellow star-like crystals; decomp. 251-52°	12.44	12.05	—	—
(CH ₃ O). C ₆ H ₄ .CHO 4 1 (Anisaldehyde, 2.04 g., 0.015 M)	After 10 mins. heating.	23.1	67.6	Golden yellow leaflets; charred 240°; decomp. 247°	12.02	12.24	28.71	28.57
(OH). C ₆ H ₄ .CHO (Salicylaldehyde, 2.84 g., 0.02 M)	Heated for 1 hr. & kept overnight.	1.90	55.1	Yellow feathery leaflets; charred 220°; decomp. 266°	12.71	12.76	30.34	29.80
(OH). C ₆ H ₄ .CHO 3 1 (1.84 g., 0.015 M)	After 20 mins. heating.	2.38	71.6	Yellowish green leaflets; charred 134°; decomp. 300°	12.84	12.76	28.81	29.80
(NO ₂). C ₆ H ₄ .CHO 4 1 (2.27 g., 0.015 M)	Heated for 3 hrs. & kept for 3 hrs.	0.62	17.2	Pale yellow leaflets; decomp. 218°	16.70	15.64	27.09	27.30
(OH) ₂ . C ₆ H ₃ .CHO 2 : 4 1 (β-Resorcylic aldehyde**, 1.38 g., 0.01 M)	Heated for 2 hrs; pptd by Ac ₂ O (1 c.c.) & AcOH (10 c.c.) & warmed.	1.50	34.9	Dark red; charred 270°; soln. in hot ACOH, green fluorescence	8.63	9.79	23.45	22.84
(HO) ₃ . C ₆ H ₂ .CHO 3 : 4 : 5 1 (Pyrogallol aldehyde)	After 40 mins. heating.	1.80	50.0	Tiny red plates; charred 220°	11.11	11.60	27.32	27.14
(CH ₃ O)(OH)C ₆ H ₃ .CHO 3 : 4 1 (Vanillin, 2.28 g., 0.015 M)	After 10 mins. heating.	1.70	48.0	Yellow leaflets; charred 260°; decomp. 270°	11.54	11.69	27.80	27.30

Condensations of Malonylguanidine with 2:4-Dihydroxy-, 3:4:5-Trihydroxy-, 3-Methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehydes and with Furfural.—The condensations were run exactly as in the previous experiment, with malonylguanidine (0.635 g., 0.005 M). In the case of vanillin glacial acetic acid, saturated with hydrogen chloride, gave equally good result. All the products were decomposed by water giving the combined acid and the aldehyde back. Concentrated sulphuric acid and formic acid dissolved them with the evolution of hydrogen chloride in the former case and colour change to golden yellow in the latter case. Aqueous alkalis produced transient red-orange colorations in the case of the di- and tri-phenolic compounds. All the products had deeper colour than the bis-type of compounds and their composition tallied rather with an arylidene-malonylguanidine chloride. The results are summarised in the following table.

* This 'Ar' is the same as signified by that of the aldehyde used.

** The figures agreed with that of a diacetylated reaction product.

TABLE II

Ar-CHO & wt.	Formation of the compound.	Yield		Colour, shape & charring point.	Arylidene-malonylguanidine chloride. (Ar ⁺ CH: C ₂ H ₃ N ₃ O ₄ .HCl) Nitrogen HCl			
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
(HO) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ .CHO _{2:4} _I (β-Resorcylic aldehyde** 1.035 g., 0.075 M)	After 1½ hrs. at room temp.	1.10 g.	77.40%	Deep yellow; charred 241-42°	75.01	74.81	12.30	12.87
(HO) ₃ C ₆ H ₂ .CHO _{3:4:5} _I (Pyrogallol aldehyde, 1.16 g., 0.075 M)	After 1½ hr. at 40°	1.10	73.3	Orange blocks; charred 202°	73.81	74.02	11.92	12.20
(CH ₃ O) ₄ (OH)C ₆ H ₂ .CHO ₃ ₄ _I (Vanillin, 0.76 g., 0.005 M)	Within ½ hr. at 60°	0.58	32.2	Tiny red plates; charred 221°	14.73	14.71	11.15	12.00
C ₄ H ₃ O.CHO (Furfural), 0.72 g., 0.075 M)	Within 20 mins.	0.66	53.7	Carbonised; greenish black; infusible.	15.4	17.39	11.32	15.10

* This 'Ar' is the same as signified by that of the aldehyde used.

** Solution in formic acid of the product diluted with acetic acid gave bluish fluorescence.

Reactions in aqueous solutions under strong acidic conditions are proposed to be further investigated.

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